

A Different Look at Traffic Sociology and Driver Psychology

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To cite this article: Assoc. Prof. Kursat Sahin Yildirimer, St. Clements University, Current Science, Volume 4, No. 7-4, 2022, p. 01-33. - 0099-0001-2207-0401.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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• The magazine is published monthly.

"The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month." ("Scientific Studies - Current

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Abstract

Psychology can be defined as the study of personality as a synthesis of maturation and learning. It emerged as a science and has developed through various disciplines, using methods and techniques to consolidate itself at the operational level. The decisive development of psychology took place through the application of systems specific to the natural sciences to the study of the mind. Like all sciences, psychology uses various methods to investigate the personality of individuals. The most commonly used methods are experimental, clinical and psychoanalytic methods. The psychoanalytic method seems to be the most appropriate method for treating the driver, both when examining his abilities and when learning about traffic psychology, since it takes into account the close relationship between the analyst and the subject. With the psychoanalysis founded by Freud, the positive and negative components of the personality emerge from the conscience of the subject. Personality is the way of being human. Therefore, personality is an individual manifestation, each represented in a form that can be processed by the environment and culture in which he lives. It is a dynamic organization

of multiple aspects (cognitive, emotional, volitional, motivational) as a synthesis of maturation and learning. Perceptions of risk influence mindsets in very fundamental ways (Napier et al., 2018) and are involved in public transport decisions and behavior. Transport hazards can be both tangible (like injuries and air pollution) and intangible (like road rages) (Meller and Haustein 2018). In addition, risks are revealed and highlighted in conversation. For example, in the context of cars, concerns and fears about the outside world (exposure to crime, antisocial behavior, collisions and traffic jams), vehicle reliability (dangerous road conditions, bad weather, getting lost, slow acceleration) can be identified ((fuel and technical failure) , bodily failure (lethargy, making mistakes, and being too old to drive), and identity and self (competing with others, having a social standing, and being too slow) (Gossling 2).

Keywords: *Traffic Psychology, Driver Psychology, Traffic Sociology, Drivers and Traffic, Psychological and Sociological Traffic*

1. Introduction

As stated in many sources and studies in the literature, it has been determined that traffic safety depends on the integrated and complex relationship between various components (Bucchi, A. & Simone, A. (2000)):

- *Psychology of the driver of the vehicle,*
- *Traffic,*
- *vehicle ,*
- *environment and*
- *road infrastructure*

According to statistics, the component that seems to be the most important as it is responsible for the majority of accidents is the behavior and thus the psychology of the car driver. Since driving behavior is strongly conditioned by the perception of the road environment, it also includes designing roads that consist of harmonious and coordinated patterns and meet drivers' expectations. It is important that the driver can continue his journey without surprises or distractions that could cause him to lose control of the vehicle. Traffic, in its complexity, is

undeniably conditioned not only by vehicles, but also by drivers with different psychological characteristics, with multiform ends and purposes. As a result, situations of instability may arise where driving behavior may become irrational. The complexity of the interactions that occur in traffic changes the specific behavior of various factors. In order to have a safe circulation that respects traffic, each driver must participate, taking into account the behavior of others, and be willing to observe their common safety needs without trying to impose their own behavior. Vehicles today are increasingly equipped with assisted driving systems that relieve the driver of their responsibilities and unfortunately sometimes prevent them from paying due attention. To increase roaming safety, these devices must be detected, coded, used by the driver, who must rely on his personality-determined behavior to use it properly. The environment is made up of a complex set of factors, including the constitutive elements of road, region, traffic and weather conditions:

- *The road with its geometric design,*
- *Flora,*
- *Buildings,*
- *region through emergency points,*
- *Intensity,*
- *Composition and*
- *traffic over speed,*
- *atmospheric events,*
- *Rain, snow, wind and fog; meteorological conditions.*

In these cases, it is clear that the personality expressed through psychology is decisive on the behavior of the driver. The road infrastructure, with its geometric features, is of fundamental importance in the psychological conditioning of the driver, for which a number of precise design proposals are made. As a result, all components of the integrated and complex relationship involving air circulation safety depend, to varying degrees, on the behavior of the driver. This makes it necessary to investigate the underlying issues of the psychology of the individual who becomes a driver after he sets off. Psychology has gained significant scientific importance and has become a fundamental tool for recognizing and interpreting the behavior of the individual in a single, social setting. Consequently, accreditation of road drivers should also

include a psychological test aimed at assessing the person's ability to adopt the behaviors that form the basis of safe driving.

2. Driver Psychology

Psychology relies on techniques to achieve its predetermined goals. The most commonly used are those based on experiments, interviews, surveys, and interviews. The most effective techniques in the relationship between analyst and driver are speaking and survey techniques. These are used not only to gather information about the driver, but also to intervene, if necessary, at the therapeutic level. They make it possible to obtain useful information for personality tests and image extraction, help identify and correct behavioral difficulties, and therefore shape the driver to have a safe relationship with driving at all times and especially in emergencies. In this way, it is possible to test and obtain an individual who better complies with the roaming safety rules. From this relationship between psychology and driver we can also derive information useful for road design purposes. To test the personality of a potential driver, we need to understand how he or she is built. Structure is constructed through perception, learning, and memory.

3. Perception

An individual cannot socialize or communicate without perceiving, learning and memorizing the content of the experience. He observes reality using his senses, especially in the case of a driver:

- *Seeing,*
- *Hearing and*
- *Don't smell.*

When it comes to vision, the eye functions as a camera, catalyzing light waves through the opening of the eyeballs. A lens, the natural lens of our eye, focuses light rays and transforms them through the process of adaptation. The surface on which light rays are concentrated is the

retina. The image is upside down on the retina in two dimensions, while the third dimension, depth, is recovered by the brain.

Hearing through the ear is possible. Dimensions of hearing experience are the frequency and amplitude of sound waves. The ear amplifies the vibrations of the eardrum and transmits them to the brain. Second, it sends all impulses to the brain.

Smell is a sense that works on a chemical basis. Odor is obtained when some molecules of a substance reach the nasal cavity. Perception, therefore, can be defined as the process by which the brain acquires information through the senses and processes them to grasp reality. In the system created in this way, information is organized and becomes an important part of it. Perception is primarily based on two theories:

- *realistic and*
- *Representative theory.*

According to the realistic theory, the environment is perceived by the brain as it appears, while according to the representational theory, it is the brain that produces the reality. The two theories mutually integrate each other and together produce perception. Perceptual constancy is the phenomenon that proves that even though objects change their appearance, they are still perceived in the same shape, size, and color. Therefore, it is the phenomena that make it possible to correct the errors that the visual system produces on reality. For this reason, the brain performs an additional processing to appropriately adapt the sensory data and the same brain centers. Perceptual constancy, therefore, indicates that certain qualities of phenomena remain unchanged. Motion perception takes place in a multiform way. In this case, it is the structuring and reprocessing of data and information that the mind interprets critically.

Motion is detected through two systems:

- *image-retina and*
- *Eye-head systems.*

The image-retina system is based on image-retina exchange; The eye-head system uses eye movements that make it possible to follow the image. Motion perception can be proven with auto-kinetic effect and stroboscopic effect. The auto-kinetic effect consists of sensing the

motion of a bright and still point in a dark room. The stroboscopic effect occurs when certain static images are detected in motion. Therefore, the individual not only has the ability to describe a moving object, but also has the ability to calculate its trajectory and velocity. Thus, we can conclude that perception is a complex process. This complexity can also be observed with optical illusions. It is this series of phenomena that interests and significantly conditions the driver.

Optical illusions are visual phenomena that give the impression of perceiving objects that the eyes do not actually see. These phenomena can be explained by shape psychology.

Second, it treats the shape as a whole, not individual parts. Optical illusions are primarily created by extension illusions and direction illusions.

Extension illusions occur when the boundary conditions of an object cause a dimension other than actual size in the observer. Illusions of direction occur when the information set contains elements that tend to distort the resulting lines.

It is clear that these phenomena can cause the driver to misinterpret reality, and the more likely the driver is to lose concentration and adopt a less responsible behavior, the more inaccurate these interpretations will be.

4. Learning

Learning is a process in which an individual adopts his own behavior. To know the dynamics underlying behavior, we need to be familiar with the learning process. Learning is manifested not only by the need to observe and explore, but also by the need to experience the surrounding reality. Acquiring the dynamics and processes involved in learning is very complex. There are two types of learning that interact with and digest each other:

- *The first is for the acquisition of concepts,*
- *The second is based on lived experience and motivation to learn.*

The second type, which is undoubtedly more important in the driver situation, requires joint biopsychological and mental involvement. Based on a sense of exploration and discovery, it is

self-motivated and contributes to changing behavior when the subject learns.

During the learning process, the individual makes his own experiences and participates in many situations, referring to knowledge from the past with his intelligence and sensitivity. They change their behavior, rearrange them according to what they have learned, and adapt to the environment. Experiments on learning have produced different theories. Those on conditioning, trial-and-error learning, and social learning are most relevant to explaining driver behavior.

Conditioning theory has allowed us, in part, to explore human instincts. The theory of learning by trial and error focuses on gradualism, in which an individual develops with experience and gradually develops his or her ability. Social learning or learning by imitation is a theory that demonstrates the importance of the environment for adopting behavior acquired through imitation. Therefore, psychology tells us that the driver learns the driving behavior and thus the safe driving behavior through experience.

Unfortunately, the development of theories and experiments has shown that not all people have the ability to be safe drivers. In many cases, the person can even learn the method of driving, but does not know how to apply it, or may put it into practice too late when the event requires short periods of time. This fact may be seen throughout the individual's life due to intellectual and/or psychophysical limitations, or alternatively it may arise for other reasons.

For these reasons, there are two main reasons that are important for the driver. First, it consists of a temporary lack of ability when the person is subject to numbing of their powers for possible reasons, such as temporary psychophysical states such as taking medication or drugs. The latter can be determined by old age, which causes a weakening of the reaction. Clearly, the potential driver must be psychologically analyzed to discover and predict his learning-provoking psychophysical state and thus determine his suitability for driving.

5. Memory

Memory or mnemonic activity is an integrated process that refers to a dynamic vision of reality. For this reason, memory is subject to constant changes and transformations, as it is characterized by dynamism. Therefore, memory is not only an activity in which information is

seen, encoded and stored, but also has the ability to use previously acquired things. There can be two types of memory operations:

- *In the first, the concepts on which the individual thinks and reason are mainly composed of remembered elements. Therefore, thanks to the flexibility, power and usability of previously perceived facts, we are able to use the concept of time by referring to the past and making predictions. In reality, an event is remembered through reconnection and reintegration. Stimulators of reintegration are memories of experiences that occurred at a particular time in the past.*
- *In the second type of memory process, it can be seen that many manifestations of past experiences are not capable of reconstructing the past. In the case of a driver, the first type of memory process is activated when driving, even when traveling for the first time, when elements of the road and boundary conditions refer to experiences gained.*

The second type occurs in automatic actions such as opening the door to get into the car. The problem lies in the fact that the two processes should not be mixed. As a matter of fact, if the driving behavior occurs without paying the necessary attention, the second memory process comes into play and it is clear that this situation is not compatible with safe circulation conditions.

Therefore, the driver must have reached a mentally mature state in order to be able to respond to stimuli in a manner consistent with the initial memory process, whatever the circumstances. The construction of memories is not chaotic or haphazard, with reference to the recall processes discussed; rather, it is the result of the degree to which the information is encoded. The most comprehensively organized and cataloged memories are the hardest to forget, although there are interventions. In other words, information learned initially may prevent the memory from collecting information about subsequent events, and vice versa. Because of these behavioral patterns, the driver's psychological maturity is an important characteristic that should be properly evaluated. Oblivion is another type of interference that can occur. It can happen for various reasons, such as spontaneous deterioration of some information after a certain period of inactivity, interference of certain data with the already held data, and the unconscious removal of certain information. In the event of an initial deterioration due to lack of use, a

reliable driver should be capable of forgetting as late as possible. In the case of data interference, the driver's mentality needs to be logical and effective in order to get rid of or at least significantly reduce the inconvenience caused. Finally, an example of unconscious elimination occurs when the mind no longer has its original potential, which usually happens as a natural consequence of aging.

To summarize, mnemonic activity is the capacity to take on behaviors that are consistent with past experiences and learning to activate the process by which past learning leaves traces in the mind that can be translated into changes in behavior patterns. This is done to improve one's ability to remember information from the past.

As a result, memory, learning and communication are deeply intertwined and interdependent. Without mnemonic activity there can be no learning, and without learning there can be no knowledge, and without knowledge there can be no communication with others. This is the driver's challenge when on the road and surrounded by other vehicles, each driven by a different type of driver. To better understand how memory works, we can start by considering that there are essentially three different forms of memory:

- *Momentary,*
- *short term and*
- *Long-term.*

An immediate memory is a sensory memory that is temporary and only lasts a short time. A photographic technique is an incomplete process for hearing and an iconic process for visuals that makes it possible to remember things and images with pinpoint accuracy. Instant memory is the memory that allows the driver to perceive the path and its features and store all this information subconsciously. Instant memory also helps the driver make snap decisions. The peculiarity of short-term memory is that it allows what is perceived and selected by the immediate memory to be stored for a limited period of time, and commonly represents a piece of information in a code that reflects a person's physical characteristics.

In addition, short-term memory has the ability to store what is perceived and selected by the immediate memory. It is possible to transfer information to long-term memory by reviewing it. Memory stored in the long term can potentially last a lifetime. It is a mnemonic system that

makes it possible to store information for an unlimited period of time through various procedures and retrieve it later. Information recovery is clearly the most important and decisive step for the driver. Information recovery must occur through rigorous coding and orderly storage of what is observed and must be able to last over time.

6. Behaviour

After examining the fundamental mechanisms of perception, learning, and memory, the next step is to explore the emotional and motivational processes involved in the driver's behavior and decision making. Some kind of emotion is always there whenever you see human behavior. This manifests as a highly charged emotional state accompanied by changes in psychophysiological functioning. As a direct result of the complexity that separates emotions, emotions have been characterized in various ways throughout history .

The first is determined by the way the autonomic nervous system and the central nervous system communicate with each other. It is the responsibility of the central nervous system to organize and collect information produced by the body's peripheral organs and systems.

Emotional behavior requires the participation of the whole brain, but specifically the right hemisphere, which is the part of the brain responsible for fantasy, imagination and creativity. Cognitive functions are responsible for the development of emotions through activities of interpretation, evaluation and conceptualization. It is possible to analyze the impact of membership in a social group on one's emotional experiences, taking into account the environmental and cultural dimensions of emotions. Studies on motivation have shown that there is a close connection between emotionality and physiological structure within the person.

In fact, motivation consists of cognitive, emotional, social and physiological components that condition behavior when combined in an interaction process. For this reason, it is possible to define motivation as a process that provides the behavior to obtain observable and variable results by producing the necessary spiritual energy related to the environment in the individual. This definition of motivation is consistent with the concept of intrinsic motivation. But psychological energy and action are not always triggered by motivation. Sometimes they are

activated by other factors. Actions that are thought through and done over and over again lack motivation.

In any case, psychology research on motivation must have a dual focus:

- *First, it must be able to predict behavior and*
- *Second, it must be able to influence behavior by directing it towards concrete goals.*

Behavioral theory is the theory that provides the highest level of assurance about the correct interpretation of emotions. Taking the need-impulse component as his starting point, he went on to show that learning leads to motivation after making this assumption. Our behavior is made up of various behavioral systems, each of which is a collection of habits based on innate and/or learned elements. These factors may be present at birth or acquired over time. Some systems go through a physiological phase governed by variables present at birth. Others are guided by the experiences and lessons that the person has often learned throughout his or her life . Unfortunately, aggression is a regular feature in drivers, and one of the things that contributes to this trend is its innate nature.

An example is when the person in the traffic expresses many forms of aggression covertly and indirectly, for example, when he swears, insults or makes sarcastic remarks. In most cases, being aggressive is a response that saves a person from feeling frustrated. The driver must undergo a psychological evaluation to determine firstly what kind of person he is on a basic emotional level, and secondly, whether his ways of understanding and analyzing reality are correct. After that, we need to encode the link between behavior and emotion. In this context, the person acting as a driver is given the task of illuminating the impulses that set him in motion, by investigating the factors that are assimilated and continue to affect the subconscious. This research will also make it possible to gain a reaction on the driver's tendency to aggression, which we can call "road anger", which is usually uncontrolled and typically only occurs when driving.

7. Behavior in social settings

Constant relationships are formed between the person and the society in which he lives. In his life, he is the one who inspires and builds partnerships with those like him; summarizes the past as social experience, the present as ongoing action, and the future as the creation of collective consciousness. Therefore, the person discovers that they are placed in seemingly incompatible conditions, such as being free to make decisions but still constrained by social structures. For this reason, since he is looking for ways to fully realize his independence, he seeks ways to overcome all kinds of restrictions, and this causes his behavior to become quite radical in the partnership process.

As a result, a scenario has been created where actions are followed by reactions and stances are intertwined with counter stances. As a direct result of this, the personality of each individual becomes external in society and therefore the synthesis of the actions of individual members of society. The individual, on the other hand, is not lost in society, it continues to be a dynamic component at all times and under all circumstances. So, society is not the arithmetic sum of all these individual activities; rather society is the result of each individual activity. As a result of this situation, the individual shapes and communicates aspects of his personality. Personality is expressed through one's attitudes, which serve as a means of communicating to oneself the myriad aspects of each component present in everyday reality. As a result, attitudes depend not only on personal experience, but also on the surrounding social environment.

Although the individual's behavior is often in line with what he says he believes, he often has irrational views. Basically, multiple components are responsible for conditioning one's attitudes. One of the components is the product of one's opinions, beliefs, and assumptions that cause the individual to classify other individuals, objects, and conditions through predictions and judgments. The second component has an emotional character and takes its origin from the collection of feelings and emotions that represent the acquired and innate baggage of every human being. The formation of this component comes from a set of feelings and emotions that every person has. These two aspects are deeply intertwined, which creates a strong bond between them. In fact, the first component determines the goals that the person wants to achieve and what techniques he will use to achieve these goals. Second, it depends on the motivating and dynamic aspects of an attitude and on the interaction with people, objects and situations that each person perceives in certain circumstances.

As a final point of discussion, as we have shown, an additional component is formed by the individual's psychological trait, also conditioned by the environment, which can lead to the assumption of irrational behavior in the individual. Therefore, the driver does not only display his personality while driving; rather, it also reflects a set of social conditioning. This is the case because driving is a social activity. These conditionings can have positive or negative effects on the individual. In fact, we need to investigate whether the driver is able to manage his attitude in the sense that he chooses to adopt positive and consistent attitudes, or whether he is susceptible to irrational behavior that is unquestionably harmful to the safety of the circulation. Finally, we need to determine how the driver will react when faced with abnormal situations that are established and executed by the social environment. The capacity of the driver is determined by the findings of a research on social or group psychology.

8. Review Procedures

Considering all the factors discussed above, it is clear that looking at the theoretical and practical knowledge currently needed is not sufficient to determine whether it is sufficient to obtain a driver's license. No one can safely operate a motor vehicle physically and mentally in changing traffic conditions. In addition, we need to make a psychological analysis of the individual's behavior as well as his attitudes.

9. Related Considerations

In recent years psychology has made significant advances and continues to find application in ever-expanding fields. Unfortunately, the primary focus of these applications is to understand and evaluate the behavior of a 980. On the other hand, it goes without saying that there is a psychological link between the driver and the infrastructure in the field of transportation . This connection is not simple, but rather intertwined. The result is difficult as it depends on a wide variety of factors that are simultaneously related to the driver and the surrounding infrastructure. It is integrated due to the ability of several components to affect and interact with each other.

As a direct result of this, it would be correct to challenge the approach often used when constructing roads by proposing the use of polynomial lines in the axis creation process. There has been controversy over the importance of boundary conditions in relation to driving behavior. Consequently, given the complexity of the problem at hand regarding the development and management of road infrastructure, we need to change road infrastructure. Strategies used up to this point should be reassessed by adding a psychologist and sociologist to the group of engineers, urban planners, and economists.

10. Transportation Sector and Human Relations

There have been brief periods when transport studies have offered an optimistic view that the era of the private car is about to end. This view was supported by concepts of "peak car", representing more critical views of the automobile. Other contributing factors to this view included increased urban interest in cycling and the observed decline in driving license (Delbosc and Currie 2013; Goodwin and Van Dender 2013; Pucher and Buehler 2008). However, despite many advances in transportation systems, there is statistical evidence that the number of cars used will continue to increase. At the same time, vehicles are becoming heavier, bulkier and with heavier engines (IEA (International Energy Agency) 2019; OICA (International Organization of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers) 2020).

For over a century, several industries have been at the forefront of efforts to promote the automobile. Oil interests, automakers, and construction companies have had a significant impact on the expansion of transportation systems. This allowed material provisions to intertwine with socially entrenched transportation needs and dependencies, as well as to construct narratives that fed economic structures, power relations, and automobile norms (Norton 2008; Urry 2013). Since the 1920s, transportation infrastructure in the Western world has generally been developed for the individual automobile on the principles of anticipation and delivery (Hutton 2013; Wollen and Kerr 2002).

Given the scientific consensus on the many detrimental effects of increased automobile use on society, it is surprising that there has been such a persistent interest in automobile culture.

This work seeks to unravel the connections and differences between domains, as well as providing important insights by exploring explanations for transport behavior in individual human traits and traits of the mind. The article will focus specifically on:

It is noteworthy that major themes in the field of transport behavior studies, including identity, gender, and attitudes, have been explored from the perspectives of various academic fields. Many of these perspectives are complementary and provide new insights when compared. The article is structured as a discussion of different perspectives that converge and complement each other. It also revisits the new mobility paradigm to summarize key ideas and insights from the social sciences and then highlights the links between these ideas and psychology. The findings are used in the process of compiling a list of factors that require special attention.

11. Shift of Paradigm to Mobility

Urry (2000) observed that people and objects both symbolize flows and that the concept of "travel" encompasses not only physical activity but also mental travel, virtual travel, and even imaginary travel. This concept is called the "new mobility paradigm" and was devised by Sheller and Urry (2006). They declare that it is necessary to go beyond a "static" social science and to understand society as a "fluid" concept. In today's society, objects, people, and ideas all move at "various speeds, scales, and viscosities." In addition, there are areas of "disconnection, social exclusion, and inaudible" as well as filters that "limit, direct, and govern movement" (Sheller and Urry 2006, 210, 212, 213). According to the new mobility paradigm, which states that movement is all-encompassing, movement encompasses everything, including people, ideas, pictures, information, diseases, garbage, legal and illegal goods, power and risks.

As society accepts or tolerates these flows, flows change society; and where mobility is the norm, they transform from possibilities to requirements (Cresswell 2006). (Haustein and Hunecke 2007). For example, the decision to have bodily mobility no longer exists, "because immobility signifies stagnation, deterioration, and inferiority" (Faist 2013, 1640). The proposed level of coercion is so great that the person is no longer a 'sovereign, autonomous actor' but a 'carrier and in some ways even a product of actions in which he participates' (Schwanen and Lucas 2011, 22). Thus, patterns of mobility include cultural practices and social norms in the

context of complex interrelationships, including people, technology, knowledge and emotions (Sheller and Urry 2006). When life is lived in the present moment and in motion, identities can become more fluid (Gossling and Stavrinidi2016; Wilson and Obrador2022). Bauman(2000) used the term "fluid modernity" to describe this phenomenon.

The proliferation of smartphones and the widespread use of social media has accelerated the development of various forms of liquidity. According to Germann-Molz (2012), information and communication technologies improve people's lives by allowing better coordination and coexistence, and an increasing percentage of individuals are open to simultaneous digital and analog lives (Mills 2016). Sheller and Urry (2006) referred to the merging of transportation and communication while describing the evolving types of coexistence. The way mobilities are realized, evaluated, communicated and desired in today's world is inspired by ICT (Hajli, Wang and Tajvidi 2018; Liu, Wu and Li 2019). Physical activity measurements can be taken by a wide variety of measures, including flight miles, amount of energy used (in calories or fuel), number of countries visited, and number of steps taken each day. Performance and comparison of the mobilities as well as visualization through travel stories, posts or maps are carried out here. There are millions of people who follow popular travel bloggers and Instagrammers, as well as celebrities, as they build their personal brands around constant patterns of activity. According to Gossling (2019), the change in social norms caused by role model mobility affects ideas of sociability, connection and friendship while reshaping notions of identity at the same time. There are also reflections on how time is perceived, given that being always online (Mills2016) and being in a "state(s) of persistent distraction" (Carr2020,112) implies concentration on both the here and now.

12. Mobility Contexts

While mobility is discussed in a wide variety of transport contexts (Adey, Budd and Hubbard 2007; Volden and Hansen 2022; cycling; Freudendal-Pedersen 2015; public transport; Bissell 2010), perhaps the 'wonderful domination' of the 'civil society' automobile system and the automotive system is the most has attracted much attention (Sheller and Urry 2000, 755). Our perceptions of space, distance, and the social rituals we participate in are all subject to and

influenced by cars (Braun and Randell 2021; Thrift 2004; Merriman 2009; Sheller and Urry 2000). Cars literally make it possible to have fast lives (Schwanen and Lucas 2011). According to Urry (2000, 59), "the significance of the automobile is that it reconstructs civil society by introducing unique ways of living, traveling, and socializing in and through an automobileized time-space." Urry (2000) suggested that the automobile dominates society because of the space and resources it requires, its adverse effects on the environment (from vehicle accidents to air pollution), and its geopolitical implications (including conflicts over oil). (Sheller and Urry 2000; Urry 2013). Cars play an important role in people's daily mobility in many nations, and the cultural significance of this fact has been the subject of much debate (eg Cohan and Hark 1997; Wollen and Kerr 2002). Consequently, it constitutes a suitable crossover for the integration of mobility study into psychology, a science with its own research methodology and research focuses.

13. Transitioning to a New Mobility Paradigm and Its Links to Psychology

According to Sheller and Urry (2000, p.738), automobile is one of the most important products of consumer consumption and is defined by 'sign values' such as speed, home, safety, sexual desire, job success, independence (family, masculinity and genetic reproduction). . They also note that the car is anthropomorphized in the sense that it is associated with human characteristics (like aging), personalities (like "rebel"), and names. Although Sheller and Urry (2000) refer to automobiles as "things made" (ibid. 738), the authors implicitly agree that the automobile can be transformed from an object to a subject by the application of human interpretation (name, age).

Sheller (2004) also relies on an inherently psychological interpretation in his discussion of automotive emotions. He concludes that "[...] feelings about driving are central to understanding the stubborn persistence of car-based culture as well as more technical and socio-economic factors" (Ibid.,223), while also 'what we feel inside and inside the car'. He also makes his observations (ibid., 228). There is an emotional bond between people and their cars. For example, Sheller (2004, 225) recognizes that cars are sexualized objects, classifying them as "phallic" or "feminized". He concludes that "the car embodies the personality and is involved in the ego formation of the owner or driver as competent, powerful, capable, and sexually desirable" (Sheller 2004, p. 225). Sheller (2004) examines the emotions of anger, joy, pleasure,

or desire for protection in his subjects. All these components, including biological needs (such as security, community, and reproduction), emotions (such as anger, defiance, and control), and personality and identity-related traits (such as superiority) are reflected in (evolutionary) social psychology (self-confidence and aggression) (Deffenbacher, Stephens). and Sullman 2016; Galovski and Blanchard 2004; Mesken et al. 2007; Sullman 2015; Zhang and Chan 2016).

The issue of car identity may be the area where the connections between the new mobility paradigm and psychology are most readily apparent. According to Seller (2004), socialization in vehicle culture can begin in early infancy. This results in the reproduction of automobile-related norms (Urry 2004). As a result, sociologists have linked the car to social identities (both in-group and national), which may be reflected in the types of cars used, traffic laws, driving habits or vehicle cultures (Edensor 2004; Urry 2004). Self-identification and comparisons with members of other groups contribute to the formation of a person's social identity (Abrams and Hogg 1990; Hogg and Terry 2000). Ideas of personal identity are linked to ideas of social identity; however, they are flexible in relation to factors such as experiences during infancy, the social environment in which they were raised, or comparisons with others (Giddens 1991; Phillips and Daniluk 2004). According to Mellstrom (2004) and Uteng and Cresswell (2008), personal identities in automotive situations can be associated with masculinity, dominance or power. Getting a driver's license is a rite of passage, the granting of maturity (Muuss 1970); Cancellation of license is the acceptance of old age and incompetence by the society. The automobile can issue or receive identification (Buys and Carpenter 2002). Driving a car is defined by Schwanen and Lucas (2011, p. 25) as "a social activity that is social and, arguably, important and essential for the creation of personal identities as well as personal identities".

14. Examination of a Person's Identity-Related Functions

There are additional connections to psychology to be discovered in examining the functions of a car linked to one's identity. "The body of the car offers an extension of the human body," says Sheller and Urry (2006, 24). "The car body surrounds the fragile, sensitive and vulnerable human skin with a new steel skin." Because of the vehicle's capabilities (speed, navigation) as

well as its protective value, the automobile has been characterized as a more complex human technology mix of an "exoskeleton" (Graves-Brown2000) and a "hybrid car driver". " (Edensor2004,116) (derived from car and person; Michael 2000).

These point to the potential of holdings that involve combining a driver and a vehicle into a single operational unit. This will result in the realization of driver identities through the car, where the car's make and type, driving styles or names may be expressions of self-concepts projected onto the car (Gossling 2017). When the car takes on such roles, this will also result in the realization of driver identities through the car. For example, bumper stickers have the potential to be seen as personality warnings (eg skulls, spiders). In situations where there is a significant amount of time spent together, drivers can gain a sense of shared identity with their vehicle.

It is even possible to give the car its own identity and personality. According to Baudrillard and Evans (1991,313), individuals, and more specifically drivers, give agency and purpose to the automobile, which is a type of 'personality' and 'becomes a subject moving on its own'. This idea was presented in their article. This is probably more evident in movies about cars, where cars are often shown moving of their own accord (eg Christine, The Love Bug, Transformers). The concept of elevating a car with personality from object to subject is commonplace in automotive advertising ('This is much more than a car'). It all depends on the path that takes you down). The self-driving car can make its own "decisions", which contributes to an increased sense of autonomy for the vehicle. According to Mellstrom (2004), the automobile's ability to overcome the obstacle of being a subject from being an object depends on the driver's personality as well as the conditions. There is also gendering of identity attributions (Uteng and Cresswell 2008). According to Mellstrom (2002), men are more likely to form (masculine) identities in relation to machines and technology. This is particularly important in the context of 'violent (male) mobility' (Balkmar 2018) or 'burning masculinity' (Redshaw 2008), both of which are characterized by a tendency for men to engage in aggressive behavior. The significance of these findings in the field of transport research lies in the fact that people have rights when using objects (driving, transmitting) (to space, right of way, noise, pollution).

15. Sociological Concepts of Travel and Traffic

Sociology has also drawn attention to the branches of seeing cars in traffic environments as representations of their invisible drivers behind windshields, even when traveling at moderate speeds. Urry (2004, 29-30) has observed that people who drive are "exempt from regular etiquette and face-to-face contact with all those people occupying the road." This is because the driver's face is hidden behind the windshield. Urry concluded that the car did not allow for "reciprocity of the eye" and instead the car became a representation of the driver. Indeed, psychological research has shown that anthropomorphized automobile designs such as eyes, noses, and ears are seen as similar to human features (Windhager et al. 2008, 2010). Once again, there are links with psychological concepts:

According to Neuberg, Kenrick, and Schaller (2010), the purpose of facial expressions in human biology is to describe attitudes and emotions; as a result, cars can be considered either benevolent or hostile (Graves-Brown 2000; Landwehr, McGill, and Herrmann 2011).

The public's perception of recognizable features on the 'faces' of cars is supported by the fact that car fronts are increasingly geared towards inducing fear (Windhager et al. 2008). Also, personality traits can be communicated through the naming of automobile models (Piller 1999). For example, some cars with aggressive names are Annihilator, Charger, Ram, Raptor or Super Marauder. According to Gossling (2017), the interrelationships between characteristic manifestations and their perceptions are not well understood, but lend credibility to the hypothesis that cars serve their role of relieving anxiety, inducing fear, or imposing domination.

This description of automobile functions is not intended to be complete, but demonstrates the usefulness of integrating sociological and psychological perspectives when trying to understand transportation systems and behavior. Concepts discovered by considering the dual perspectives of the two fields will result in the production of extra insights. The discussion also shows that the new mobility paradigm introduces a large number of psychologically related concepts. This provides clarity to studies that might otherwise be hazy: If car ownership is associated with 'freedom' (Sheller and Urry 2000), what can psychology tell us about the feelings of oppression that must be behind interest in such car functions? (Graves-Brown 1997)

If car ownership is associated with 'freedom', then what can car ownership afford? What can psychology tell us about the reasons behind choosing a lifestyle that requires constant movement? If, like the mobility perspective discussed by Wilson and Obrador (2022), is a home that is both a place and a journey, then what can psychology tell us about the underlying reasons for choosing a lifestyle that requires constant movement? According to sociologists, the automobile serves a variety of purposes, including "home, security, sexual desire, success at work, independence, family, masculinity, genetic reproduction" (Sheller and Urry 2000, 738) and "mentalities, emotions, or behaviors." The second includes "rebellion" and "escape" (Graves-Brown 1997). Emotions and the more fundamental aspects of human biology are open to a more enlightened interpretation when viewed through the prism of psychology.

16. To Extend the Scope of the New Mobilities Paradigm

Traffic and transportation psychology are the study of cognition and performance, that is, aspects of transportation systems that can be as diverse as perceptions of speed, reaction times, concepts of risk, anger, sensation seeking, gender differences, policy interventions, habits, transportation system designs, or pro-environmental behaviors (Rothengatter and Huguenin 2004). Psychology has three different subfields: social psychology, evolutionary social psychology, and clinical psychology, all of which have a significant impact on mobility. These subdomains are as follows:

A layer of understanding complementary to the perspectives that characterize the field of mobility is provided by the study of psychology, which can be thought of as an extension of the field in the sense that it is a discipline. It would be appropriate to focus on personality traits and features of the mind.

It is widely known that social psychology relates to the field of transportation studies, and this is also the area where many of the links to mobility research can be explored. Although the importance of other transportation values has been recognized since the 1970s, many people still believe that their decisions about transportation make sense.¹

¹ (Andor et al. 2020) (for mobility see eg Flink 1975).

The distinction between instrumental, symbolic and emotional values was proposed by Steg (2005). Instrumental values include things like speed, flexibility, convenience, and safety. Symbolic values include such things as opportunities for expression of social position or self, comparison with others, and social norms (emotions evoked or pacified). For example, certain car brands and models can be used as an indicator of the income level of the owner, and the sign value can be obtained by posing with just one vehicle (Hennighausen et al. 2016). Within the framework of desires for safety, emotional values are important (Bauman 2007), but the automobile is also associated with a wide range of emotions, from anxiety to sexual excitement to rebellion (Gossling 2017).

Further insights can be gained through the study of evolutionary social psychology, which takes human wants and needs as its starting point. According to the findings presented by Neuberg, Kenrick, and Schaller (2010), humans are the result of evolution, a process in which emotions and certain behaviors play important roles. All the emotions that drive human behavior, including love, jealousy, hatred, friendship, betrayal, fear, courage, aggression, and cooperation, are ultimately linked to reproduction. There are many connections to be made with transportation culture in areas such as self-preservation, resource acquisition, attractiveness, dignity, partnering or raising children. For example, responses to fear play an important role in the evolution of mammalian species, as they depend on survival. These reactions include freezing, running away, fighting, fear and fainting (Bracha 2004). Cars not only provide protection, but also function as a method of exit (Bauman 2007; Graves-Brown 1997). Navigation is an act that is seen as an expression of territoriality, that is, a claim on the disputed territory. Specifically, navigation is a claim on disputed territory (Collin-Lange 2014). According to Gossling (2017), cars are used as a way to mark territorial boundaries, announce their combat capabilities, and challenge other drivers with the soundscapes they produce. These sounds include low engine growls, engine roars and revs. The color of cars has evolutionary significance: Among monkeys, the color red indicates a primate's fighting capacity and establishes a hierarchy: Guéguen et al. (2012), drivers of other vehicles are more likely to act more aggressively when they see a red car. Automobile semiotics such as loudness, colour, facial features, conspicuousness or size and mass are all reflected in roles associated with

reproduction (Sundie et al., 2011), reaffirming the importance of evolutionary social psychology interpretations of transportation systems.

In conclusion, clinical psychology is concerned with the diagnosis and understanding of mental disorders, as well as the study of how the human mind interacts with "the physical, emotional, and social elements of health and dysfunction" (Plante 2005, 7). Long ago, it was established that there are links between behavioral patterns, individual characteristics, and disorders. For example, Galovski, Malta, and Blanchard(2006,42) mention the following regarding aggressive driving:

In addition to personal predispositions such as trait anger, hostility, narcissism, and sensitivity to perceived attacks, it appears to be susceptibility to stress and external pressures, perceived behavioral control of driving, anticipated regret, positive attitudes towards aggressive driving, and subjective personal tendencies.

In addition to alcohol and substance use disorders, some aggressive drivers may suffer from serious psychiatric conditions such as borderline personality disorder and antisocial personality disorder or ADHD (attention deficit hyperactivity disorder).

There is some evidence linking mental illness with aggressive behavior in public transport settings. For example, those suffering from alcoholism and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder are more likely to drive aggressively (Yu, Evans, and Perfetti 2004). According to Gossling (2013), mental disorders are related to safety, security and subjective well-being (fears, risks; antisocial behavior; suicide), identity (self-image and individuality, power, control and dominance), and there are emotions that affect transportation behavior (aggressions and moods). In a study of people with mental health problems, Mackett (2019) found that transportation options and travel decisions are affected by fear and panic attacks. Mackett found that a wide variety of phobias are linked to traffic, and this was confirmed by the study's findings. According to Gossling and Eckert (2008), who conducted a study on communicative violence, there is also evidence that automobile advertisements target people with mental problems.

17. Mental or Emotional Difficulties

Trauma, which can be defined as challenging events that cause mental or emotional difficulties, is a factor in the development of disorders (Scaer 2014). According to Wittchen and Hoyer (2011), exposure to traumatic events is quite common. These events can be as diverse as war, child maltreatment and neglect (including physical, sexual or emotional abuse), bullying, (domestic) violence, crime (or witnessing crime), death of a loved one or close friend, or surgery. (Everett and Gallop 2001; Scaer 2014; Trumbull 2008; Whitfield 2010). Injuries are one of the most common causes of trauma, and the automobile system is inherent in such events. According to estimates provided by the WHO (World Health Organization) (2020), there are currently 1.25 million people who die on the roads each year, with the number of injured up to 50 times higher. (WHO (World Health Organization) 2020). This puts half a billion people at risk of being directly involved in accidents for a decade. In particular, "traffic accidents" can also be an expression of trauma. Studies have shown that cars, trains, and airplanes are associated with an increased risk of suicide (Kenedi et al. 2016; Gossling 2017; Peck and Warner 1995). In conclusion, there is a substantial body of data suggesting that mental illnesses, traumas, and phobias all have an impact on transportation behavior, and that transportation decisions and the consequences of traffic contribute to trauma and phobias. Therefore, clinical psychology has become an extremely important field of study in the field of mobility research, where the violence inherent in cars has already been identified (Braun and Randell 2021).

As Adey, Budd and Hubbard (2007, 776) point out, the new mobility paradigm extended "beyond the definitions of flows to the social and technological processes that created them". Similar to this discovery, the study of psychology can help to understand the conditions underlying transportation choices. These conditions refer to the mental states that inspire, influence, and command transport behavior. Discussions on transport behavior, such as those presented here for the vehicle, would benefit from adding analytical depth through more systematic integration of ideas from psychology in mobility research. The findings also have implications for understanding transport networks in more general situations. These findings are described below as a list of insights from psychological research and recommendations for extending mobility research.

18. Networks of Access to Both Symbolic and Emotional Roles

Many people continue to believe that decisions about modes of transport, for example as a function of cost, are intrinsically "rational" (Andor et al., 2020). The field of mobility highlights the importance of symbolic and emotional values associated with transport, with additional information from the field of psychology. According to Gossling (2017), the automobile serves several purposes, including as a vehicle for social stratification, as a way to demonstrate authority, as a way to rebel, and as a way to seek pleasure. There are links to other forms of transport; For example, passengers flying on commercial airlines may display frequent flyer status cards in their luggage to symbolically claim status around the socially stratified airport environment (Adey, Budd, and Hubbard 2007). Public transport creates emotional environments of vulnerability and sensitivity (Bissell 2010). Cycling has been associated with experiencing positive mental and physical health (Singleton 2019). This connection has both symbolic ('cyclists fitter') and emotional ('I feel happy') components, reflecting different emotional states. Emotional qualities also contribute to the underdevelopment of e-scooters as recreational means of transportation (Christoforou et al., 2021). An idea developed by psychology's explanation contributions to mobility is that decisions about modes of transport are rarely made for purely instrumental reasons.

19. Transportation Options and Behaviors

Personalities can be inferred from transportation preferences, and psychographic segmentation can be used to characterize those who use various modes of transportation (Haustein and Hunecke 2013). For example, personality factors play a role in a person's choice of car brand, and research has shown that high-status cars are more likely to be involved in violence (Lonnqvist, Ilmarinen, and Leikas 2020). Confrontations with traffic can be emotionally challenging and provoke certain behavioral responses from drivers. For example, anger is a common emotion among drivers (Deffenbacher, Stephens, and Sullman 2016) and is linked to impulsivity, narcissism, and disrespect for social norms (Hennessy 2016). It is especially important to keep this in mind while driving, as the combination of high speeds, written and unwritten norms, anonymity (while driving) and quick contacts can lead to conditions fraught

with discomfort, difficulty and danger (Hennessy 2016). According to Sullman (2015), people with a personality trait known as anger are more likely to engage in violent behavior while driving, and this anger feature can be strengthened by anger experiences while driving (Hennessy 2016). Anger behind the wheel increases the likelihood of taking risks and having an accident (Bele et al. 2020) and may even escalate into road rage (Agerwala et al. 2008; Sharkin 2004). Another study showed that there is a relationship between road anger and a mentally unstable personality state (Sansone et al. 2010). Research has also been done on driver personality traits related to excitement seeking and impulsivity, anger and hostility, emotional stability or instability, and conscientiousness (Dahlen and White 2006; Jonah 1997). Deffenbacher et al. (2003), Herrero-Fernández (2016), and Zhang and Chan (2016), any type of aggressive driving contributes to an increased likelihood of traffic accidents. Characteristics of an individual's personality can influence their decisions and actions in different transport settings (eg Bissell 2010, Mackett 2019). The field of psychology has made significant advances in our knowledge of the interrelationships between these concepts.

20. Behavioral IDs

There is a complex web of connections between one's social and personal identities and many modes of transport. For example, the automobile is important for both personal and social (national) identities. This is true both in the past and today (Ruvio and Shoham 2011). Although Hogg and Terry (2000) claim that social identity is based on intergroup comparison and differentiation from other groups, personal identity can be understood in relation to social identity. An individual's sense of who he or she is variable, subject to change throughout their lifetime, and open to the possibility of various manifestations (Giddens 1991; Phillips and Daniluk 2004). For example, a single individual may have two identities, one as a driver and the other as a cyclist (Murtagh, Gatersleben, & Uzzell 2012). Drivers may also have a shared identity to which identity (and personality) can be attributed to their vehicle. This is an identity that may have emerged as a result of social needs, phobias, or traumatic events. According to Ruvio and Shoham (2011), car-based identities may be associated with more positive self-perceptions, and restrictions on driving can be seen as a threat to one's identity (Murtagh, Gatersleben, and Uzzell 2012). In such cases, resistance stems not from the lack of available

transportation, but from identity issues. For example, the German far-right's 'we love diesel' campaign (Arning and Ziefle 2020) uses a policy of fear to achieve authoritarian and anti-environmental goals that ultimately attack social and personal identities (Muradian and Pascual 2020). Another example of this can be seen in the ongoing battle for gender equality and the preservation of feminine identity in modern Saudi Arabia, where the struggle is focused on the importance of the automobile (Tsujiigami 2020).

Interconnections with one's identity can also be seen in different kinds of settings. Young adults can have aspirational frequent flyer identities modeled after the lifestyles of celebrities (Liu, Wu, and Li 2019) and express and reaffirm their own frequent flyer identities via social media (Gossling and Stavrinidi 2016). Frequent flyers express evolving air passenger identities (Cohen, Hanna, and Gossling 2018). Cyclist identities have the potential to generate bicycle culture and bicycle-centered urban social identities (Aldred and Jungnickel 2014). The degree of strong ownership of certain identities (such as driver, cyclist, and pedestrian) is another factor that influences the ease with which people switch between different modes of transport (Murtagh, Gatersleben, and Uzzell 2012). These results are derived from research bodies in the fields of mobility and psychology.

21. Concerns and Concerns Influence Transportation Choices

Expanding frameworks of inequality, insecurity and competition define the characteristics of today's global society (Piketty 2014; Sassen 2014). Distinct disasters, such as the financial crisis in 2008, the Syrian refugee problem in 2011, and the worldwide COVID-19 pandemic that began in 2019, all contributed to reinforcing the notions that Beck's original risk society theory was correct (1986). In a risk society where risks are global and intangible and Beck (2007) defines the risk society as a "risk society", fears define "attitude towards life" as well as "anticipation of disaster" (28-29). Anxieties in modern life in Western culture are prevalent in a wide variety of dimensions, including economic instability, environmental degradation, or self-construction in the age of social media (Giddens 2011; Hoge, Bickham, and Cantor 2017). As a result, there is a greater need for safety and protection, a focus on Self, and a simultaneous loss of empathy for others. This is because threats are justified and necessary defenses are made

(Bauman 2007; Beck and Beck-Gernsheim 2002; Halman 1996; Konrath, O'Brien and Hsing 2011).

Vehicle manufacturers take advantage of these concerns by using various advertising methods that play on people's concerns to promote the reassuring qualities that come with buying a car. It is also possible that news in the media supports predetermined notions of danger, as in the context of active mobility (Fevyer and Aldred 2022).

It is a fact that fears have an impact on transport behavior, which is clearly demonstrated by the changes in transport modes that occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic (Mouratidis and Papagiannakis 2021; Shortall, Mouter and Van Wee 2021). Since anxiety consumes cognitive resources and impairs one's ability to focus, high levels of anxiety are directly related to the increased risk behind the wheel (Dula et al. 2010). Programs such as safe parking for women, train security cameras, and emergency app developers aim to alleviate concerns; however, by justifying and reinforcing these fears by making them a point of contention, these programs ultimately fail. Concerns have been raised about security, discrimination, aggression and inappropriate use of customer information in the context of mobility services (Henama and Sifolo 2017; Rogers 2017). Cyclists deviate from important roads to avoid air pollution, noise, or roads believed to be unsafe; they can also navigate sidewalks to avoid "vehicle space" (Ihlstrom, Henriksson and Kircher 2021). Public transport infrastructures have been developed to appeal to the "ideal travelers" (Lubitow, Rainer and Bassett 2017), despite creating fearful places for other people (claustrophobic architecture; Gossling 2018; infection risks; Afshinnekoo et al. 2015). Discussions about whether e-scooter and cyclist users should wear helmets show different perspectives on the hazards posed by traffic participants and insurers (Molina-Garca et al., 2018). Fears were also gendered, as women reported that they felt less safe while driving, despite the real dangers associated with sexual harassment, abuse, or violence in public transport (Taylor et al. 2011) (Gekoski et al. 2017). In other cases, the hazards inherent in a particular mode of transport add to its appeal. Terry et al. (2015) sees races as sites for masculine images. However, according to Gossling (2017), these competitions can also be seen as symbolic escapades. Information on the role that anxieties and fears play in transportation behavior is currently limited and could benefit from insights from both the field of mobility and psychology.

22. Both Mental Health and Transportation Behavior Are Interlinked

In addition to personality disorders, mood, thought or behavior disorders are what is meant by the term "mental illness" (American Psychiatric Association 2012). There is a relationship between mental illness and travel behavior (Galovski, Malta, and Blanchard 2006). For example, substance use disorders can lead to aggressive driving; psychotic disorders may result in antisocial behavior in public transport; mood disorders can lead to the inability to look at other people in traffic; Driving can be done as a form of entertainment, leading to car chases and even suicide attempts. Those who suffer from anxiety disorders are more likely to avoid certain forms of transportation, purchase substantial automobiles, or have panic attacks. Sleep problems can increase the likelihood of an accident, and dementia causes a person to be unable to drive. Gossling (2013) and Gossling (2017) have found that some types of trauma can cause people to lead hyperactive lives, commonly known as flight responses, or seeking hazards in traffic. Phobias such as amaxophobia (fear of traveling in a car or vehicle), aerophobia (fear of flying), and cyclophobia (fear of cycling) are examples of phobias related to transportation behavior (fear of cycling). A general fear of travel, commonly known as hodophobia, can lead to more sedentary lifestyles. Due to feelings of isolation, some people find themselves on frequent trips, such as driving aimlessly (Mokhtarian and Salomon 2001). According to Mackett (2019), fears and other mental health issues apply to travel by all means of transport. There is also an association between poor mental health and physical disorders such as obesity and disability. For example, being overweight has been associated with increased automobile use and larger vehicle sizes (Li, Liu, and Zhang 2011). This again leads to lack of movement and weight gain (Frank, Andresen, and Schmid 2004; Swinburn et al. 2011), highlighting the complex relationships that exist between mental health and transportation behavior. The clinical psychology field is primarily responsible for the knowledge of these complex relationships.

23. Transportation Result in Community Benefits

Choices and behavior in human transportation can be influenced by human biology. It is in the interest of organisms to reproduce their genetic material, which requires them to find suitable

mates (Dawkins 2016 [1976]). People are brought closer together by means of transport, whether geographically or for a common interest. This is most clearly seen in the example of the automobile, which serves both as a place for seeking sexual partners and as a setting for sexual behavior (Struckman-Johnson et al. 2017). Cars have complex indicators:

their size, shape, or brand may express importance, power, authority, or resourcefulness; their color may indicate fighting ability or arousal; their eyes may indicate compatible or aggressive personality types; and motor sounds can stimulate mental states (Gosling 2017).

According to Gosling (2017), popular culture, and especially car movies, can reinforce concepts of reproductive success as they promote forms of driving, flirting, and consensual (and forced) sex. This is especially true when it comes to interracial relationships. Membership in interest groups (such as automotive organizations, car clubs, and car or ridesharing), auto professions, car events, online communities, and car media also offers a wide variety of opportunities for the community and fulfills people's need for social connection. While the vehicle is responsible for most of these public transport services, other modes of transport can play similar roles, including: Public transport brings large numbers of people together; hiking, trekking, and other slow-moving activities provide opportunities for casual encounters; cyclists are often organized in ways similar to the automobile community; frequent flyers report their status with status cards that also provide access to members-only lounges. All these perform fundamentally important human tasks, including sociability, connectivity, and mate-seeking. Knowledge of these interrelationships is limited, and it may be possible to expand this understanding further by looking through the lens of evolutionary social psychology.

24. The Automobile is the Symbol of Freedom and Independence

Different people are exposed to various stresses or types of pressure that can be categorized as psychological pressure (Merton 1957). Pressure can be the result of events that occurred in the past or that occurred during childhood or adolescence, such as physical or emotional abuse or neglect at home, at work, at school, or through social media. Other types of restrictions and restrictions, such as quarantines, mandatory military service, and tax payments are examples of

what some people see as oppressive government systems (Grasse et al., 2021). This can cause people to have the impression that "bad authority" is responsible. From this point of view, rebellion is a form of opposition consisting of refusing to accept rules and questioning accepted social norms. Stealing, escaping the situation, engaging in physical conflicts out of the need for revenge, and drug abuse are all examples of coping techniques (Agnew 2008; Link et al. 2016). Boys and adolescents are more likely to react with hostility and violence than girls. Reactions are gender specific (Reid and Piquero 2016). In the context of cars, "riot" has been studied in relation to illegal street racing, honing, stance and coal rolling (Gossling 2017). France's Yellow Vest movement and other violent demonstrations have been fueled by the country's carbon price (Jetten, Mols and Selvanathan 2020). Milder types of disobedience such as idling, as well as more aggressive ones, such as damaging traffic signs, even with a firearm, are examples of riots (Boggs, Heaslip, and Louisell 2013). Reasons for the challenge may include sabotaging or malfunctioning of speed cameras, as well as sudden accelerations that cause significant air pollution or illegal parking. This may also apply to other forms of transport; For example, the clutter and destruction of public transport may be a representation of a so-called 'payment'. But resistance, revenge, and flight are the primary ways in which rebellion manifests today. The main reason for this is the widespread use of automobiles. While more research needs to be done in this area, both the field of mobility and psychology provide several methodological advances that can be taken to study the phenomenon in question.

25. A Community's Mental Health Can Be Removed from Transport Networks

The way in which transportation systems are designed and used, and the characteristics of these systems, are largely a mirror of the socio-psychological situation of the society. Dimensions of car size, mass and motorization; driving under the influence; hitting someone and fleeing the scene; stealing a bike; destroying electric scooters; damaging traffic infrastructure are indicators of the levels of empathy, materialism and anger that exist in a society. For example, large SUV shares in national car fleets may be an indication that the population is feeling insecure; the growth in car mass can be interpreted as a need for dominance; higher motorization may reflect readiness to flee or a desire to surpass competition, and increased hit-and-run numbers may indicate decreased levels of personal responsibility. In particular, in an increasing number of

incidents, the automobile is also used as a weapon, i.e. deliberately used to threaten or injure individuals. This is an important point. A change in the mental state of society is likely to be reflected in the increased use of angled (and therefore hostile) automobile headlights and elements designed to deter, such as many lights resembling "spider eyes". Although no studies seem to have been done to examine these links, we can still see them in popular culture. Trauma themes such as the death of a parent, neglect of a parent, or physical abuse by a parent are common in many profitable movie series, from Transformers to Fast and Furious. These themes have great appeal to audiences all over the world. Another common point of all these movies is that driving is shown as the best way to solve any problem (Gossling 2017). There is also evidence of opposite trends: higher cyclist shares will reflect a growth in sympathetic values. This is supported by research. Cars and motorcycles powered by silent electric motors do not compete with other vehicles or drivers in the noise department. While not enough research has been done on these interrelationships, it is clear that they exist at a fundamental level and can be studied using methods common to the disciplines of mobility and psychology.

26. There is Resistance to Change in the Transportation System for Psychological Reasons

There is a substantial body of research suggesting that efforts to promote a change in transport behavior are ineffective. Often this can be explained by unexplored psychological tensions within the individual. For example, Bauman (2007) noted that in the United States, marketing stimulates concerns and high SUV sales reflect a world believed to be dangerous. This evidence was based on the idea that marketing in the United States reinforces concerns. When drivers are forced to evaluate personal safety against societal goals such as climate change mitigation, cognitive dissonance can be caused by the perceived need for self-protection. Gossling (2013) explains that this may contribute to cognitive dissonance. As a result, moving towards smaller cars that are less harmful to the environment can lead to rationalizations such as "climate change is not real" or "my impact is too small to be meaningful". This is important because the case illustrates why attempts to reform transport policies can have counterproductive results and even confirm the government's skepticism. Advice on cognitive dissonance, school runs (trips

that should be 'safe' for children), helmet campaigns (driving safe versus looking good), speed limits (reducing emissions or saving travel time) or the 'safety' of public transport (and thus emphasizing risks)) apps. Although they are expected to have a significant impact on the success of planning and design interventions as well as marketing efforts, the interrelationships are still poorly understood. It is possible that research based on mobility and psychology will help further develop this discipline in the future.

27. Useful of Psychological Findings in the Construction of Policies

Psychology also has a significant impact on the formulation of public policy, given the complex arrangements offered by the various modes of transport. In the context of urban transport, interventions often aim to reduce levels of motor transport, particularly the use of private cars, and increase the use of public transport and active forms of mobility. There is a substantial amount of data showing that nudges, app changes, and appeals actually have limited, and often even contradictory, effects. (Gossling 2017) identifies messages of fear and guilt, sarcasm, social isolation, and public humiliation as examples of campaigns that could be considered "problematic" from a psychological perspective. Policies expressed using this basis will almost always fail to attract support, leading to submission, rejection, opposition or anger. In light of this, serious consideration should be given to communication methods and attractive designs. In theory, interventions can be designed with either logical or emotional appeal as their basis. For example, urban transport planners can justify spending on bicycle infrastructure using the logical argument that cyclists create accessible space. This argument can be based on the fact that cyclists create free space. A design with an emotional appeal can highlight the fact that cyclists are healthier, based on the idea that it is desirable to be a physically active person. In many different situations, transportation interventions have effectively included components of psychology previously; however, it is possible that this is not always obvious or done intentionally. The concept of Stadtradeln is based on the community, the fulfilling feeling of being part of a group that shares their passion for cycling. This is another poorly researched area of research and has links to both the mobility literature and the discipline of psychology.

28. Results

The new mobility paradigm revealed that transport behavior should never be discussed without considering its social functions and understanding of a society composed and shaped by various flows. This was done to explain the fact that it is impossible to discuss transport behavior without taking into account its social functions. The purpose of this article is to expand the epistemology of mobilities by arguing that psychology adds a complementary layer to the understanding of transportation decisions and choices. This recognizes that bearing behavior reflects and responds to biological cues and social needs such as anxieties and fears, finding a community and finding a partner. It reaffirms the importance of events such as trauma, phobia, neglect and abuse as contributing factors to the formation of personalities and individual identities. Taken into account, these dimensions account for various types of resistance and aggression, as well as dependence on certain means of transport. Because it is primarily influenced by the principles of empiricism, psychology provides different epistemological advances from qualitative research, which focuses on behaviors, meanings, beliefs, or institutions that organize and regulate activities. The integration of transport psychology and mobility research is fruitful for knowledge acquisition as it makes it possible to explain the motivations underlying transport behavior in constructing theories. This provides value in the sense that behavior and decisions can be more appropriately described, avoiding explanations that are too narrowly obtained and ultimately incomplete.

29. Resources

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